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THE NEXUS BETWEEN PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE: SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE AND PSYCHOLOGICAL RESILIENCE AS MEDIATORS

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The Nexus between Physical Education and Academic Performance: Spiritual Intelligence and Psychological Resilience as Mediators

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Abstract

The current study analyzes the interrelatedness of physical education and academic success of the students in the universities hailing from Punjab, Pakistan and how spiritual intelligence and psychological resilience mediate this relationship. While the benefits of physical education in the body are well documented, the benefits are arriving of physical education on the mental and psychological aspects of education. The study will employ the quantitative survey, with the collection of data from higher educational institutions in

Punjab. It is observed in study that students with respect to participation in physical education activities and spiritual intelligence, self-knowledge, meaning-making, perfection and holistic knowledge, psychological resilience, which is capacity to withstand hardship and sickness. For this purpose, the study uses validated measures. In order to conduct the study systematically, some hypotheses were developed from the theoretical framework of current study to test the hypothesized relationships and reaching the desired conclusions thereby extracting new and innovative information used for decision making and contributions. The study used statistical procedures to assess direct and indirect effects of physical education on students' performances academically. Evidence shows there is a robust relationship between involvement in physical education and enhanced academic performance. In addition, there is a partial mediating effect of spiritual intelligence and psychological resilience. This means that students that practice physical education tend to increased spiritual intelligence, psychological resilience, which are then positively related to academic performance. The results confirm the need of all-inclusive educational system that mixes the spiritual, physical, and psychological magnitudes. The present study suggests that education institutions respect physical education as means of improving the students' mental, physical wellbeing and, emotional development. Additionally, it recommends and

regard further education curricula, with students' assistance programs and future examination to boost sustained academic success possible over the varied physical education programs.

Keywords: Physical Education, Academic Performance, Spiritual Intelligence & Psychological Resilience, Mediation

INTRODUCTION

The association between physical education and student performance is the long-term research question in educational research, and evidence indicates that participation in physical activities has a positive impact on cognitive and mental health, and well-being of the student. There are various direct and indirect ways in which physical education is related to academic achievement [1]. Nevertheless, the processes, which determine this correlation, are complicated and multi-layered. In this respect, the psychological resilience and spiritual intelligence play a central role in determining the influence of physical education and pedagogy in education in its broadest sense on the academic success [2]. Therefore, direct positive effects of physical activities during education are enhanced performance, and generalized better learning [3]. Such advantages become motivation, increased concentration, and more engaging learning activities, in their turn, lead to academic success.

The emotional paybacks are, the lower anxiety, positive mood, and greater emotional, social, and cognitive development [4]. The activities of movements facilitate side effects to other emotions and psychological gains like elevated mood and self-esteem. The emotional development, social refinement and general cognitive enhancement structure is led by holistic growth. The spiritual intelligence is capacity to apply spiritual values and wisdom to solving problems, self-reflection, and significant social connectivity [5]. It addresses communication, team work, problem solving, and leadership skills in the academic activities, which motivate collaborative pedagogy. This can involve such practices as meditation, on ethical empathy and conduct [6]. This also includes one having self-awareness, purposeful moral character and compassion. In the framework of physical education, mindfulness-promoting practices well-being of students, nurture growth of spiritual intelligence in students.

When students have the perception that they are not just carrying out their activities without purpose, then they are more inclined to commit and to take the initiative to continue with their studies in accordance with their values. It is also helpful on the anxiety and stress management that hinder academic performance [7]. Spiritual intelligence offers purpose and moral compass to the students, intrinsic motivation therefore can be seen as

moderator which results in better performance and dedication to studies [8]. The students with greater spiritual intelligences are superior solving interpersonal problems, cooperation as well as offering a favorable climate to improve learning, add to academic performance [9]. Emotional equilibrium and calmness that are brought about by spiritual practices make capable of remaining focused and resilient. As such, their spiritual intelligences facilitate empathy, social cohesion, and intelligence because they are of higher order.

One can be resilient psychologically to change and flourish despite obstacles, stress and misery and the parameters that are required is optimism, perseverance, emotional control, and problem solving. Other skills involved in it include optimism, perseverance, emotional regulation, and problem solving. Engagement in physical activities leads to characterization of self-discipline, perseverance, and hardiness and also psychological strength since winning hard times is one of the major aspects of physical education [10]. This gives a self-supporting academic favorable perspective since students can overcome the setbacks fast [11]. This attitude which is important in academic success are as a result of success in the physical education as they trigger the skill of overcoming the academic pressures [12] and failures and also develop resilience which enables students to approach their work with confidence and determination. The characteristics result in improved outcomes.

The faith in the good things is the critical component of self-efficacy as it enables students to address challenges directly and proceed with their work even when it is difficult. Psychological benefits of exercise are numerous as well. It is established to decrease cortisol, hence creating a relaxing and more concentrative state of the mind [13]. It assists students to approach work more easily, and promote spiritual intelligence which consequently, improves motivational and psychosocial resilience enabling students to easily cope with complicated challenges. These are the correlates of stress, academic achievement [14]. It is these stress correlates that preclude wholesome academic and non-academic growth. This allows the students to face the challenges of academics with intent and psychological will [15]. The students who participate in sports activities that instruct and behavior, and mindfulness may most likely become wiser spiritually and more vigorous.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The development of emotional intelligence is facilitated by physical education as such skills are very critical in workforce and education settings, enhance working, leading, and communicating of students with

others and themselves [34]. Psychological resilience is the capacity to handle stress and misery, capacity to adapt and recuperate to difficulties and to recuperate when faced with problems and to spring back after difficulties. Team sports imply the activities in which empathy, leadership, resolution of conflicts is required [35]. Moreover, social sports activities and other activities also train one to be able to navigate through social situations and develop social intelligence. The aspect of physical education assists in creating resilience in a way that exposes students to circumstances that are challenging and need endurance and self-control [36]. Thus, these difficulties are even implicit in physical activities by the notions of opposition, failure, and successes.

It requires emotional regulation, coping, and growth mentality to overcome life and academic stress [37]. This is what physical education imparts to the students and can be applied in real life. Strong students can cope with stress more easily, they become more motivated, overcome adversity and solve complicated problems, and all these are critical to academic success [38]. This approach is aimed at making all round students and not only in education. The physical education acts as bridge that connects intelligence with the psychological resilience to create education experience [22]. The benefits of physical education on intelligence and resilience are mutually reinforcing. Improved cognitive and emotional intelligence through sports enhances resilience, while increased resilience supports better performance and cognitive working under stress that provides the developmental opportunities to students concerning the behavioral and attitudinal consequences.

The learning continuum has included more balanced understanding of learning, which involves aspects of movement, cognition, emotion and social well-being [11]. While pedagogy has focused more on the dimensions of latitude, the last couple of decades has seen addition of dimensions of broad psychological and spiritual relevance that shape the wellbeing and academic performance of the learner [14]. Educational psychology has shown the need to develop spiritual intelligence, which involves self-inquiry and exploration of purpose of existence and relationships between elements of life outside the material world [17]. Because of the impact of particular psychosocial and spiritual processes which improve academic performance, a more integrated understanding of impact of physical education on academic performance is warranted. As studies have shown, physical education has been shown to improve sense of self, self-reflection, and harmonization of the body and mind.

Though physical education contributes positively to the overall health and fitness of the body, the impact the body has on the spiritual and psychological functioning is even further ability to impact the body on the cognitive, emotional, and learning profiles of individuals [20]. Another important component, which combines achievement on the academic front with the physical education, is psychological resilience, which is the ability to handle and adapt to the challenges of adversity, stress and failure [23]. Educational attainment is a multi-dimensional measure that refers to the complexity of the problem in the issue of physical activity and mental health such as motivation and coping skills and the primary burden [27]. The interconnectedness of physical education and academic performance and the spiritual and psychosocial fortitude that can be achieved through this interconnection are perhaps the best examples of the holistic view of the education for developments.

This combined perspective serves to inform educators, policymakers and researchers to improve academic attainment through multidisciplinary approaches which encompass physical, mental and spiritual aspects of individual [30]. As student faces various academic and social challenges in the sphere of higher education, addition of physical education to curriculum should serve as supportive mechanism to achieve holistic student development [32]. It equips individuals with self-awareness, resilience, moral reasoning, and better understanding of the challenges of life leads to adoption of positive academic behaviours perseverance, self-motivation and emotional self-regulation, emotionally stable equipped with better coping mechanisms to handle stress, leads to greater effort to achieve success on examinations [34]. The resilience is gained through education challenges of physical stress, establishing coping mechanisms and positive mindset to deal with the stress.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is quantitative in nature that aims to examine relationship in chasing the hypotheses and reaching conclusion. The positivism approach was used to chasing relationships among research variables (physical activity, life satisfaction, and motivation) of study. The research approach specifies the way through which data is collected from the respondents by retrieving them to reach their answers about variables of research in order to reach required conclusion through justification towards desired outcomes. The population of interest in this research is students hailing from colleges in Punjab, Pakistan wherein 2890 students from colleges wherein a sample is drawn from population (351), has been extracted by using the sampling formula widely used in the social research studies. Thus,

351 questionnaires were distributed among which 341 were recollected and used for analysis. Similarly, the random simple technique was used to access the population of study which comes under the non-probability technique to ensure required data from diverse dimensions. Also, both secondary and primary data were used to collect data from respondents and from existing knowledge databased to analyze data to reach conclusion. The questionnaires were adopted from previous studies. Similarly, 5-point Likert scale was used to record responses of respondents about research issues in particular context to access respondents and achieving desired outcomes.

RESULTS OF STUDY

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
Physical Education	336	1.30	4.80	3.0886	.83762
Spiritual Intelligence	336	1.80	4.60	3.1709	.84420
Psychological Resilience	336	1.70	4.70	3.4563	.58882
Academic Performance	336	1.50	4.62	3.3214	.66770

The descriptive statistics are used to examine the description about the research variables from different perspectives like sample of the study, maximum and minimum responses rates towards the physical education, spiritual intelligence, psychological resilience and academic performance through different statements for measuring the variables, mean of the responses and standard deviations in response rates towards the research variables of study. The results of current study thus revealed that all the values are within the acceptable range therefore ensuring significant descriptive analysis.

Reliability Analysis

Variables	Items	Cronbach Alpha
Physical Education	10	0.89
Spiritual Intelligence	10	0.78
Psychological Resilience	10	0.72
Academic Performance	10	0.86

The results of reliability statistics through Cronbach Alpha revealed information about internal consistency that exists amid the research variables of present study. The results showed that with respect to physical education (CA = 0.89 & Items = 10), spiritual intelligence (CA = 0.78 & Items = 10), psychological resilience (CA = 0.72 & Items = 10), academic

performance (CA = 0.86 & Items = 10). In this linking, the reliability statistics revealed that all the values were above the threshold values and consequently suitable reliability is in acceptable range while ensuring the suitable internal consistency among the research variables likewise physical education, spiritual intelligence, psychological resilience and academic performance in study toward desired leading outcomes in the study.

Correlation Analysis

		Correlations			
		[1]	[1]	[1]	[1]
Physical Education [1]	Pearson Correlation	1	.315**	.503**	.445**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	336	336	336	336
Spiritual Intelligence [1]	Pearson Correlation	.315**	1	.397**	.396**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	336	336	336	336
Psychological Resilience [1]	Pearson Correlation	.503**	.397**	1	.587**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	336	336	336	336
Academic Performance [1]	Pearson Correlation	.445**	.396**	.587**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	336	336	336	336

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation procedure was used in this study for examining the association concerning the strength and direction in the relationship thereby using the correlation procedure to confirm the hypothesized relationship. The results of correlation offer significant information in analyzing the association among the research variables likewise, predictor and mediators are significantly associated with dependent variable of study like physical education and academic performance (R = .445 & P = .000), spiritual intelligence and academic performance (R = .396 & P = .000), psychological resilience as well as academic performance (R = .587 & P = .000), which therefore confirmed the required association among research variables and thus hypothesis was accepted from these findings.

Regression Analysis

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	SEE
1	.631a	.398	.393	.52022

Regression Analysis

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	59.504	3	19.835	73.291	.000b
	Residual	89.849	332	.271		
	Total	149.353	335			

Regression Analysis

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	SE	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.774	.176		4.400	.000
	Physical Education	.139	.040	.174	3.498	.001
	Spiritual Intelligence	.134	.037	.170	3.617	.000
	Psychological Resilience	.490	.058	.432	8.394	.000

a. Predictors: Physical Education, Psychological Resilience & Spiritual Intelligence

b. Dependent Variable: Academic Performance

The regression procedure was used for determining the cause-and-effect relationship among the research variables likewise the physical education, spiritual intelligence, psychological resilience and academic performance to confirm the prediction of academic performance through physical education, spiritual intelligence, and psychological resilience. The results revealed that there is 39.8% variance in the academic performance through physical education, spiritual intelligence, and psychological resilience. The results also confirm the individual role of each variable toward academic performance like physical education ($\beta = .139$ & P-value = .001), spiritual intelligence ($\beta = .134$ & P-value = .001), and psychological resilience ($\beta = .490$ & P-value = .001), thus hypotheses is consequently accepted.

Mediation First Step (a)

Model Summary

R	R Square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.3153	.0994	.6438	35.6734	1.0000	334.0000	.0000

Table 4.12: Coefficients of Regression (H3)

Model	Coefficient	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	2.1894	.1655	13.2316	.0000	1.8639	2.5149
Physical Education	.3178	.0532	5.9727	.0000	.2131	.4224

Predicting Variable: Physical Education
 Criterion Variable: Spiritual Intelligence

Mediation Second & Third Steps (b & c)

Model Summary

R	R Square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.5203	.2707	.3271	56.1892	2.0000	333.0000	.0000

Table 4.14 Coefficients of Regression (H3)

Model	Coefficient	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.7339	.1632	10.6255	.0000	1.4129	2.0549
Spiritual Intelligence	.2245	.0437	5.1412	.0000	.1386	.3104
Physical Education	.2835	.0450	6.2953	.0000	.1949	.3721

Predicting Variable: Physical Education, Spiritual Intelligence
 Criterion Variable: Academic Performance

Mediation Fourth Step (c)

Model Summary

R	R Square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.4451	.1981	.3586	62.4319	1.0000	334.0000	.0000

Coefficients of Regression

Model	Coefficient	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	2.2255	.1535	14.4966	.0000	1.9235	2.5274
Physical Education	.3548	.0449	7.9014	.0000	.2665	.4432

Predicting Variable: Physical Education
 Criterion Variable: Academic Performance

The mediation procedure was used in current study to examine the mediating role of spiritual intelligence in concerning physical education and academic performance in particular context through four different paths of mediation while determining the direct relationship among these variables and indirect relationship. The results of all the four paths revealed important leading information about the mediation procedure and confirmed that spiritual intelligence mediated partially the relationship between physical education and academic performance in particular context. The results showed partial mediation due to decrease in coefficient value

from (.3548) in direct relationship to (.2835) in indirect relationship while all the p-values remained vital and significant in the mediation procedure and thus hypothesis about the mediation was partially accepted due to the significant changes in coefficient values in direct and indirect relationships among the research variables of current study thereby reaching the required conclusion as well as making the decision.

DISCUSSION

The physical activity increases brain development, promoting cognitive function and indirectly, physical education fosters range of positive emotional and psychological states, such as reduced anxiety, enhanced self-esteem and improved mood and promotes holistic growth by fostering emotional, physical, social and cognitive development [38]. The spiritual intelligence is defined as capacity to smear spiritual principles and wisdom in solving problems, considerate oneself, and meaningfully linking with others [39]. It inspires communication, teamwork, problem-solving skills and leadership competencies that are appreciated in academic settings. This might include practices like meditation that emphasize ethical empathy and behavior [40]. It involves attributes like compassion, self-awareness, moral integrity and purpose. In physical education context of, activities that promote mindfulness, likeness and holistic well-being foster spiritual intelligence among students.

The things that are valuable in terms of physical education can provide education and spiritual insights by incorporating lifelong learning practices that support the presence of mindfulness, self-awareness, reflection, kindness and moral reasoning. Being involved with athletics and sports has psychological opponents, maintaining integrity [41]. In addition, the significance of athletics and sports engagement promotes necessary social, personal and academic capabilities like subsequently assists in promoting the high degrees of engagement and inspiration in all their academic and physical activities [42]. These activities and self-reflective exercises help to awaken students to analyze and resilience that or the capacity to adapt, and to be able to work effectively in the presence of stressors, hardships or transitions. [43]. Physical education aids the development of resiliency challenges that need inter as well as intra personality flexibility and psychomotor toughness.

The positive role of physical education in health and fitness cannot be doubted. However, the influence the body and all that it encompasses has on the spiritually and psychologically even is stronger. The same can be said about the influence of the body on the cognitive, emotional, and the learning profiles of the individual as well [44]. Another significant factor is

psychological resilience that combines and which is concerned with the competence to endure and adapt to the pressures of the negative situations, anxiety, and failures [45]. The academic performance educational success constructs have numerous influences' aspects being of physical activity, as well as mental health that includes motivation coping mechanisms [46]. The interdependence between physical education as well as academic performance and the emotional, spiritual and psychosocial resilience that the interdependence fosters are the best examples of the holistic approach to the education.

The educational settings have shown that spiritual intelligence due to its enhancement of coping abilities and presence of adaptive academic behaviours, is an important mediator in relationship between participation in physical activities and academic success [47]. Activities in physical education that spiritual intelligence as it enables students to achieve self-awareness and a sense of purpose and meaning [48]. Along with psychological resilience, spiritual intelligence proves to be one of strongest predictors of conversion of participation of students in physical education, to better academic results. The resilience, defined as ability to cope with the stress, challenges and setbacks, is established protective factor that contributes to academic success of students [49]. The overlapping mediatory functions of spiritual intelligence and psychological resilience, in turn, create integrated construct of benefits associated with inclusion of physical education in the educational settings.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. In physical education classes psychosocial skill development such as reflection, resilience, the teamwork, ethics, goal setting, and adaptive academic coping should be structured so students learn to generalize physical contests to adaptive coping skills and concentration in academic working environment.
2. Future research should employ the longitudinal and experimental designs in education to assess the psycho-spiritual, resilience and intensive academic contexts and calculate the long-term value of physical education in the absence of such studies towards the desired as well as leading contributions.
3. Educational policymakers need to realize the relevance of physical education both in terms of building psychological spiritual intelligence and need to adequate value time, resource allocation teacher training to make education relevant to the students' academic success rather than non-academic subject.

4. Teachers and coaches are encouraged to use supportive, mastery-oriented, and student-centered instruction that promotes self-reflection, emotional control, value-based learning as such positioned to students develop their spiritual and psychological resilience thereby enhancing academic performance.

5.3 DIRECTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

1. Future studies ought to use longitudinal and experimental designs to establish changes in psychological resilience and spiritual intelligence and the intermeditation. Future studies also ought to identify the cause-and-effect relationships between physical education and academic outcomes for success.

2. Analyzing interrelationships amid physical education, spiritual intelligence, psychological resilience, and academic outcomes, researcher ought to examine more elaborate statistical techniques like sequential mediation, and moderated mediation models to gain a better understanding of the phenomenon.

3. To increase the generalizability of the results, more cultural and contextual factors need to be integrated and more measures of psychological resilience and spiritual intelligence need to be adapted, validated, and calibrated in the different sociocultural settings, especially the non-Western ones.

4. Future studies should address various dimensions of academic achievement and measures of student growth, self-regulated learning, and self-structured learning, and wellbeing and physical education to conclude the academic benefits of physical education as required from different perspectives.

5.4 RESEARCH CONTRIBUTIONS

1. The work combines physical education with psychological and spiritual intelligence using the biopsychosocial model theory to better understand how physical education improves the academic performance of students that are required for comprehending the different and leading tasks for success.

2. The educational psychology and physical education literature are enriched by this research which shows that the relationship between physical education and academic performance is indirect and must be mediated by the psychological resilience and spiritual intelligence along with direct effects.

3. The research supports and strengthens worldwide literature by providing contextually specific evidence and underscores the importance of incorporating culturally attuned the methodologies when investigating

psychosocial processes in education in the particular contexts for developments.

4. This study enhances the mediation literature by identifying psychological resilience and spiritual intelligence parallel mediators with unique and synergistic effects in translating physical education experiences into academic outcomes that are required for completing the leading tasks to success.

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